

PLURIDENTITIES

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Work Package 5

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Main authors	Indira Wakelkamp, Marrit van de Guchte, & Inge van der Grint (University of Amsterdam, the Netherlands)

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Problem statement

The increasing linguistic and cultural diversity in Dutch education is reshaping understandings of language learning and identity, although this transformation manifests unevenly across regions. In larger cities, pupils often bring rich multilingual repertoires into school life, while in smaller towns and rural areas, classrooms tend to remain more linguistically homogeneous. Against this heterogeneous backdrop, researchers have argued that Dutch schools still tend to operate within largely monolingual frameworks that privilege standard Dutch and, to a lesser degree, English, even as societal multilingualism expands (Joubert & De Jong, 2023). Recent policy initiatives, such as the Onderwijsraad's report *Talige diversiteit benutten* [Leveraging linguistic diversity] (2025), advocate recognising home languages as learning resources, but practice often lags behind discourse.

Language is not only a communicative tool but also a central component of personal and social identity. As García and Wei (2014) and Norton (2013) argue, language shapes how individuals position themselves and are positioned by others within social contexts. For pupils who speak a language other than or in addition to Dutch at home, this link between language and identity is particularly salient. A strong sense of belonging, the feeling of being recognised and valued within the school community, forms a crucial basis for motivation and learning (Goodenow, 1993). For multilingual pupils, this sense of belonging depends to a large extent on how seriously their linguistic and cultural identities are acknowledged (Cummins, 2001; Van der Wildt et al., 2017). In the Dutch context, where classrooms vary in linguistic composition, this means that the recognition of pupils' linguistic backgrounds is not only a matter of equity but also of educational effectiveness.

Within this evolving landscape, the Pluridentities multidimensional framework (Pluridentities, 2025) provides a relevant conceptual lens for understanding how plurilingual identities develop through the interaction of four interrelated dimensions: linguistic capital, learning environment, technology, and language policy. In the Dutch case, pupils' linguistic capital can include Dutch, Frisian, or regional languages such as Low Saxon, and a wide range of heritage languages such as Arabic, Turkish, Polish, and Berber. Yet, formal education frequently separates, suppresses, or ignores these languages, limiting opportunities for identity expression.

Research conducted in the bilingual province of Friesland illustrates a gradual shift away from such language-separation pedagogies. Günther-van der Meij et al. (2020) show how

translanguaging practices, drawing flexibly on Dutch, Frisian, English, and pupils' heritage languages, help connect school learning to pupils' linguistic realities. Their findings demonstrate that when multilingual repertoires are legitimised, pupils display increased engagement and ownership of learning. Similarly, Günther-van der Meij and Duarte (2018) propose a holistic model for multilingualism in education tested in Dutch secondary education classrooms, showing that teachers who integrate multilingual strategies report greater pupil motivation and participation. These studies exemplify the learning-environment dimension of the Pluridentities framework (2025): teacher beliefs and pedagogical choices crucially mediate how linguistic capital becomes educationally valuable.

However, most Dutch teachers still express uncertainty about implementing such approaches. Joubert and de Jong (2023) found that teachers in multilingual urban regions tend to be more positive towards using pupils' home languages, while those in more monolingual areas worry about losing classroom control or fairness among pupils. Earlier large-scale interviews with Dutch secondary teachers also revealed that few felt adequately trained to, for example, integrate multilingualism into literacy instruction or classroom discourse (Kistemaker et al., 2013). These findings point to an enduring tension between inclusive ideals and practical constraints.

Recent research also points to the ways in which teachers' attitudes and classroom practices influence whether multilingualism becomes a pedagogical resource or remains marginalised. Van Beuningen and Polišenská (2019) found that while many Dutch secondary-school language teachers recognise the potential value of multilingualism, they often lack concrete strategies or institutional support to integrate it into their teaching. Their study reveals a tension between positive attitudes toward diversity and persistent uncertainty about how to operationalise multilingual approaches within existing curricula. This aligns with the learning-environment and language-policy dimensions of the Pluridentities framework (2025), highlighting how teacher beliefs and institutional constraints mediate the recognition of pupils' linguistic capital.

The technology dimension in the Dutch context remains emergent rather than foundational. Although most schools are digitally equipped, the pedagogical integration of technology into language learning varies widely. The NRO-funded research project by Van de Guchte et al. (2016) investigated how different modes of digital interaction (video, audio, and text chat) affect pupils' target-language use and motivation in modern foreign-language education, specifically English and German. Their findings indicate that technology can promote authentic communication, sustained interaction, and greater learner autonomy in the target language.

While this research does not directly address multilingual identity, it illustrates how digital environments can enhance engagement and agency; factors closely linked to the technology and learning-environment dimensions of the Pluridentities framework (2025).

Building on these earlier modes of interaction, recent developments in artificial intelligence (AI) have sparked growing interest in how tools like ChatGPT can further enhance language learning. A recent meta-study by Zhu and Wang (2025) shows that AI is increasingly used to support personalized learning, provide feedback, and facilitate communicative practice, although empirical evidence from real classroom settings remains limited. One example of such emerging research is the study by Van de Guchte et al. (in press), which explores how secondary school learners and teachers perceive the integration of ChatGPT into task-based oral interaction. Their findings illustrate both the potential of AI to reduce anxiety, support vocabulary and sentence building, and increase motivation, as well as the more modest impact on learners' live oral performance. However, systematic exploration of how Dutch pupils and teachers connect such technologies with multilingual identity work remains limited.

Taken together, these studies depict a field in transition. The Netherlands hosts significant expertise and experimentation in multilingual education, but implementation is not yet widespread. Teachers' attitudes, institutional norms, and limited professional preparation continue to shape whether multilingual repertoires are valued or marginalised. Technology, while promising, has yet to be systematically leveraged to support plurilingual learning or identity development. In this context, this working paper aims to investigate how technology, language learning, and identity interact within Dutch secondary education. Specifically, it seeks to explore how pupils and teachers perceive and enact the linkage between digital practices, linguistic attitudes, and plurilingual identity formation, through the following research questions:

- Research Question 1 (RQ1). What are the attitudes and practices of Dutch upper-secondary pupils regarding the use of technology (inside and outside the classroom) for language-related activities, and how do these relate to their linguistic attitudes and identity development?
- Research Question 2 (RQ2). What are the attitudes and practices of Dutch secondary-education teachers regarding the use of technology (inside and outside the classroom) for language-related activities, and how do these relate to pupils' linguistic attitudes and identity development?

Ultimately, this research responds to the growing yet uneven recognition of multilingualism in the Netherlands. By analysing how teachers and pupils negotiate the intersections of language, technology, and identity, it contributes to understanding how Dutch education might move beyond monolingual traditions toward more inclusive, plurilingual, and technology-mediated learning environments aligned with European and global shifts in education.

Methodology

Research design

This working paper reports on a study conducted using a quantitative research design and quantitative data analysis. It examines the attitudes and practices of Dutch upper-secondary pupils and of secondary-education teachers (from both lower and upper levels) regarding the use of technology (inside and outside the classroom), as well as the potential relation of this technology use to pupils' linguistic attitudes and identity development. The research is guided by an exploratory cross-sectional framework (Adèr & Mellenbergh, 1999). This study was approved by the ethics committee of Vrije Universiteit Brussel (Ref. No. ECHW_593-WP4-5_Phase1) and the University of Amsterdam (Ref. No. FMG-13660), and all participants provided informed consent prior to their involvement.

Participants

A non-probabilistic convenience sampling technique was employed for the selection of teachers. Eligibility was restricted to teachers working in Dutch secondary schools. Teachers were primarily reached through the researcher's professional networks, including the university's teacher education programme (e.g., in-school internship coordinators, internship supervisors and former pupils now employed as teachers) and the university's teacher professional development network. The call for participation was additionally disseminated through external professional channels, such as newsletters from subject-specific didactic networks, teacher organisations, and trade unions, and was further shared via LinkedIn, where individual teachers and professional networks redistributed the call voluntarily. Although the call was broadly circulated and open to all eligible teachers, the self-selected and network-dependent nature of participation means the sampling strategy is best characterised as non-probabilistic convenience sampling.

Pupil participation was conditional on the involvement of these teachers. Teachers who completed the teacher survey were invited to administer the pupil survey within their own classes. The pupil survey was open to pupils aged 16 or older attending Dutch secondary schools, and the survey link was circulated through the same channels used for teacher recruitment. As such,

pupil recruitment similarly followed a convenience-based model, dependent on the voluntary decision of participating teachers to implement the survey in their classrooms. As with all non-probabilistic sampling approaches, limitations regarding representativeness and the potential for selection bias are acknowledged. Accordingly, the findings are not intended to be statistically generalisable but to offer preliminary insights and rich, contextually grounded descriptions within the scope of the study. A total of 226 pupils and 39 teachers took part in the surveys.

For pupils, 43.81% considered themselves boys ($n = 99$), 53.64% identified as girls ($n = 121$), 1.77% identified as 'X' ($n = 4$), and 0.88% preferred not to say ($n = 2$). Their average age was 16.95 years ($SD = 0.77$). Moreover, reflecting the fact that Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) bilingual education programmes in the Dutch education system are generally only offered in lower secondary education, 24.34% of the participating pupils reported having been enrolled in a bilingual/multilingual programme at that level ($n = 55$), while 75.66% indicated that they had never participated in such a programme ($n = 171$). Only two schools offering such a programme were represented in the pupil survey dataset. In terms of plurilingual identity, 16.37% identified as monolingual ($n = 37$), 36.28% as bilingual ($n = 82$) and 47.35% as plurilingual ($n = 107$). Finally, 87.17% of the pupils revealed they were born in the Netherlands ($n = 97$), whereas the remaining 12.83% indicated they were born in another country ($n = 29$).

For teachers, 33.33% considered themselves men ($n = 13$), while 66.67% identified as women ($n = 27$). Their average teaching experience was 11.1 years ($SD = 8.846$). As for their plurilingual identity, 10.26% identified as monolingual ($n = 4$), 25.64% as bilingual ($n = 10$) and 64.10% as plurilingual ($n = 25$). Finally, 71.79% of the teachers reported they were born in the Netherlands ($n = 28$), while 28.21% indicated they were born in another country ($n = 11$).

Instrument and data collection

Two surveys, one for pupils and one for teachers, were constructed for the purposes of this study. Both surveys drew on items from several existing validated instruments, supplemented with additional researcher-developed questions to address study-specific aims. The selection and adaptation of items ensured both relevance to the research context and alignment with established measurement practices. Both surveys were developed by the Pluridentities consortium so as to gather information about: (1) pupils' background information, linguistic repertoire and language usage, sense of identification and belonging, school composition,

attitudes towards multilingualism and multilingual practices at school, language learning motivation and technology for language learning; and (2) teachers' background information, linguistic repertoire, sense of identification, multilingualism and language policy at school, multilingual practices, technological skillset, and use of technology to enhance language learning among pupils. For this specific working paper, only the sections related to participants' background information and technology for language learning are considered.

Both surveys include different items, in some cases expressed as multiple-choice statements or frequency selection (never-daily, also including a specific option for "for a certain period") and in others using five-point Likert scales (1 = strongly disagree; 5 = strongly agree). Before full distribution, the surveys underwent a small pilot pretest with one teacher and one pupil. Their feedback led to minor wording revisions to improve clarity. The surveys were distributed online using Qualtrics XM and administered in Dutch. Prior to responding, participants were informed about the objectives of the study and that their data would be used and stored exclusively for research purposes. Data were gathered between April and October 2025.

Data analysis

Once the data were gathered, they were exported directly from Qualtrics XM into a Microsoft Excel file for initial data cleaning, coding, and organisation. For formal analysis, the cleaned dataset was subsequently imported into R (version 4.5.2). The analysis relied on simple descriptive statistics; primarily frequency measures (counts and percentages). This initial examination summarises the basic characteristics of the sample and key study variables, providing a foundation for subsequent inferential analyses, which fall outside the scope of this working paper and will be conducted at a later stage.

Results

Pupils' attitudes towards the use of technology for language learning

Out of the 226 pupils, 195 responded to the set of questions reported on in this section. Pupils generally shared neutral or positive opinions about the use of technology to enhance their language learning. A total of 59.49% of participating pupils reported that using technology, social media, or AI tools (such as ChatGPT) helped them improve their language skills (n = 116). Moreover, the majority of them agreed that technology could provide them with easy access to resources for learning multiple languages (75.38%, n = 147).

Regarding the use of specific technologies, around two thirds of the participants revealed using social media in a language other than their home language (64.62%, n = 126), and 75.38% pointed out that they watched videos or reels on social media in languages other than their home language (n = 147). They responded neutrally when asked whether they preferred to use their home language to communicate when using social media (35.90%, n = 70), and 43.59% reported not using languages other than their home language when chatting or communicating with friends online (n = 85). Although 39.49% of pupils indicated that they never or hardly ever used AI tools to practise or learn a language (n = 77), and 31.28% were neutral on this (n = 61), 46.67% nevertheless reported that, when they did use such tools, they used them in a language other than their home language (n = 91).

In relation to their feelings of pride for speaking or learning multiple languages using technology, 43.59% of pupils were positive in this sense (n = 85), and 49.74% revealed they thought that plurilingualism was important when using technology, AI tools, or social media (n = 97). Likewise, 38.46% of pupils acknowledged that being plurilingual made them feel confident when using technology, social media, or AI tools (n = 75). Over half of the pupils, 56.92%, believed that using technology (like apps, games, or AI tools) made it easier to learn the languages taught at school (n = 111), and 48.72% thought that using technology made learning languages an enjoyable and fun task (n = 95).

Finally, when asked about whether they enjoyed their classes more when their teacher let them use technology in the class, 46.67% of the participating pupils revealed they did so (n = 91), while 41.54% showed neutral opinions in this regard (n = 81).

Teachers' attitudes towards the use of technology for language learning

Out of the 39 teachers, 33 responded to the set of questions reported on in this section. They were also generally positive about the potential of technology for language learning, language use and identity development, although a considerable number of participants showed neutral opinions. For instance, over half of the teachers revealed they did not integrate technology in their classes to encourage pupils to connect with their multilingual identities, such as using technology to explore not only their home language but also others (57.58%, $n = 19$). Nevertheless, 66.67% considered that technology could positively support multilingual education ($n = 22$), and 69.70% thought it could also support collaborative learning opportunities for pupils to practice multilingual communication ($n = 23$). Similarly, 63.64% viewed technology as a potential tool to reduce the challenges of teaching multiple languages in the same classroom setting ($n = 21$).

In relation to the integration of technology-mediated multilingual practices into (foreign) language teaching, 48.48% of the participating teachers believed they could improve pupils' motivation towards language learning ($n = 16$) while 45.45% were neutral on this ($n = 15$). Half of the teachers (51.52%, $n = 17$) thought this could also benefit pupils' intercultural awareness, and 57.58% believed it could enhance learners' confidence as plurilingual individuals ($n = 19$). A total of 42.42% felt that multilingual practices mediated by technology could improve language learning outcomes among pupils ($n = 14$), while 48.48% were neutral about this ($n = 16$).

A final point to consider is teachers' use of, and confidence in integrating, educational technology to support multilingualism in the classroom. Here, 39.39% of teachers reported feeling confident about doing so ($n = 13$), whereas 33.33% did not ($n = 11$). Furthermore, 48.48% indicated that they never or hardly ever actually used educational technology for this purpose ($n = 16$), while only 24.24% reported that they did ($n = 8$).

Technology usage for language learning and teaching

Pupils also provided information about the specific tools they used for language learning. The main findings are shown in Figure 1:

Figure 1

Pupils' use of technology for language learning

The tools most frequently used by learners for language learning were Google Translate or other digital translation tools, platforms such as Netflix or Spotify, and videos on YouTube or TikTok. In contrast, AI tools like ChatGPT or similar chatbots, video games, and language-learning apps such as Duolingo were among the least frequently used tools.

Pupils also indicated, by selecting one or more options from a pre-defined list, the language-related tasks in which they had used AI tools. Figure 2 presents the distribution of their responses.

Figure 2

Pupils' use of AI tools for language learning

As shown in Figure 2, pupils most frequently used AI for translation, although many also reported using it to obtain explanations. In contrast, AI-mediated tools were used far less often for practising conversations in another language or for writing or editing texts in another language.

Finally, teachers were asked to share how frequently they allowed their pupils to use devices in class for class-related tasks, as well as to complete assignments at home or outside of school. The results are presented in Figure 3:

Figure 3

Teacher-reported frequency of pupils' device use in and outside class for schoolwork

Regarding the use of devices such as smartphones, laptops, and tablets in class, teachers reported that they generally allowed pupils to use them multiple times a day or at least daily. Teachers also indicated that they typically asked pupils to use these devices at home or outside school with similar frequency, or alternatively on a weekly basis or only a few times per year.

Conclusions

This study examined the attitudes and practices of Dutch upper-secondary pupils and secondary education teachers regarding the use of technology, inside and outside the classroom, and its role in shaping linguistic attitudes and identity development. This working paper provides an exploratory descriptive analysis of the quantitative data, and the findings presented here should therefore be understood as initial insights rather than in-depth statistical analyses. Across both groups, the initial findings point to generally positive views about the potential of technology to support language learning, linguistic attitudes, and identity development, although neutral responses also appeared across several items. However, the actual use of technology for these purposes remained limited and inconsistent.

Pupils expressed neutral to positive attitudes towards the use of digital tools and frequently engaged with online content in at least one language other than their home language, most likely English, through platforms such as social media, YouTube, TikTok, Netflix, and Spotify. However, their active language use in digital communication was limited: many reported not using additional languages when chatting or interacting with friends. Their engagement with AI tools was also relatively low, and when they did use AI for language learning, it was mainly for receptive or support-oriented tasks. The most commonly selected uses included translation, checking or understanding meanings, and obtaining explanations. In contrast, pupils made far less use of AI for practising conversations, writing text in another language, or editing their own writing. Although pupils associated plurilingualism in digital contexts with feelings of pride, confidence, and importance, these attitudes were not strongly reflected in their actual technology practices, which remained largely passive rather than expressive or identity-oriented.

Teachers similarly recognised the potential of technology to support pupils' language learning and aspects of linguistic identity development. Many believed that digital tools could contribute to multilingual education, foster collaborative communication activities, and help address challenges associated with teaching multiple languages in the same classroom setting. Yet teachers' self-reported practices reveal a substantial gap between recognition and implementation. Confidence in integrating technology specifically for language- or identity-related purposes was mixed, and nearly half reported never or hardly ever using educational technology to support multilingualism explicitly. While teachers reported routinely allowing pupils to use devices such as smartphones, laptops, or tablets both in class and for work at home,

they seldom used technology specifically to support engagement with additional languages or linguistic identity development.

Taken together, the findings show that pupils and teachers alike view technology as having meaningful potential for language learning and, to some extent, for supporting linguistic attitudes and aspects of identity. However, in both groups, technology use for these purposes remains limited in scope. Pupils' practices were mainly centred on consuming digital content and carrying out supportive tasks such as translation or seeking explanations, rather than on more interactive or (multilingual) identity-expressive uses. Teachers, similarly, rarely integrated technology with explicit aims related to additional language use or linguistic identity development, despite recognising its potential.

This divergence between attitudes and practices highlights the need for further pedagogical support and targeted exploration. Future research could help clarify how digital tools might be used more intentionally to encourage pupils' engagement with additional languages and to better understand the role technology could play in shaping their linguistic attitudes and identity development.

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